

A Study on Financial Literacy with Special Reference to Arts and Science College Students in Palayamkottai.

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Abstract

Financial literacy is essential and considered as an additional knowledge for improving financial inclusions and also for financial stability. College students should have practical knowledge to live a better life in spite of learning only their subject. For this they should possess knowledge on financial management. Financial literacy will definitely help students to plan their daily expenses and maintain a budget to save their pocket money. The study focuses on assessing levels of financial literacy of college students of Arts and Science Students. The study focus on financial literacy with respect to demographic factors like age, gender, education. The aim of this article is to find out how far the Arts and Science college students are aware of their money handling and know about the various investment schemes and financial products for saving and find out the need for the financial literacy educational program for the students to develop their skills. Primary Data has been collected and analyzed to know the financial literacy level among Arts and Science college students within Palayamkottai in Tirunelveli District. Data has been collected through questionnaires from 110 respondents.

Keywords: Financial Literacy, Financial inclusion, Investment Schemes ,Financial Products.

1.Introduction:

Financial literacy imparts financial knowledge ,financial information and also brings change in once behaviour and their financial pattern.It gives confident in taking effective decision about their personal finance and handle their money.Very few accepted definitions and conceptual framework are there with regard to Financial Literacy on the personal finance.(Noctor, Stoney, and Stradling,1992)According to them, Financial Literacy it is the ability of making sound decisions with regard to money management.(Schagen and Lines 1996) Proper decisions made with regard to use and handling and control of money.Each and every students to overcome the financial problems should have strong financial literacy.They should learn to avail and repay educational loans and to invest their savings in proper investment schemes for their future.Most of the students find themselves in precarious fiscal situations with regard to the increasing cost of college fees,bookfees,tuition fees and other educational expenses.To overcome all these financial aspects students should be able to financially support themselves and their family.Due to lack of proper Financial education students face several financial problems.Literacy on finance to College Students is very important to initiate a savings plan,manage their pocket-money and make proper investment decision for their future.

2.Review of previous studies

- Allen &Jover, 1997¹ ; Armstrong & Craven, 1993; Baum &O'Malley, 2003; Increase in use of credit cards by college students leads to credit card debt which is a greater risk of financial problems.
- Chen and Volpe (1998)²;Through Empirical Study suggests that at young age ,students overcome financial problems such as savings and borrowings,investments and insurance and also lack financial education in college curriculum.

3.Scope of the Study:

This study is to find out the financial literacy level among Arts and Science College Students in Palayamkottai Area.

4.Objectives of the study

- To know the Financial Literacy level among Arts and Science college students and to find out how far the attitude and behaviour in savings and borrowing habits vary among Science and Arts Students .

- To find out the savings habit and ways to improve their savings habit.
- To make them understand the importance of Finance and money handling and to overcome the difficulties in future and explain the consequences in future without money and suggest measures in order to increase their level of Financial Literacy.

5. Research Hypothesis

H01: There is an association between Age group and practicing of managing personal finance.

H02: There is no significant difference among difference between the features of various Investment Schemes and the Major field of studies-Arts and Science.

6. Limitations of the study

Major limitations of the study is among Students from 5 colleges.

7. Research design

7.1. Type of research: This study is an empirical study based on collection of data through questionnaire.

7.2. Sample : Random sampling method has been adopted. The sample Population is the students studying in colleges in Palayamkottai area of Tirunelveli District.

7.3. Data Analysis: The primary Data has been collected from 110 respondents within Palayamkottai area of Tirunelveli District.

7.4. Data used: Both the primary data as well as secondary data have been collected. Primary data have been collected through questionnaire and the Secondary data have been collected from various books, journals, websites and so on.

7.5. Tools for analysis: In this study the statistical tools such as Mean, Chi-square and F-test have been used. In addition Garret ranking method has been applied for rank related questions. At many parts of the study simple percentages have been applied

8. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Gender-wise calculation of the Respondents:

Table 1: wise calculation of the Respondents

Sl.No.	Factor	Frequency	Percent
1	Male	52	47.3
2	Female	58	52.7
	Total	110	100

Source: Primary Data

The table 1 indicates that 47.3% of the total respondent are male and 52.7% are female. So the table reveals that majority of the respondents are only females.

2 .Collegewise analysis of the Respondents:

Table 2 :Collegewise analysis of the Respondents

Sl. No.	Factor	Frequency	Percent
1	SadakathullahAppa College	24	21.8
2	Sri Sarada College for women	13	11.8
3	St.Xavier's College	38	34.5
4	Sarah Tucker College for women	15	13.6
5	St.Jhon's College	20	18.2
	Total	110	100

Source: Primary Data.

The table 2 states that 11.8 percent of the respondents belongs to Sri Sarada College for Women,13.6 Percent of the respondents belongs to Sarah Tucker College for women,18.2 percent of the respondents belongs to St.Jhon's College,21.8 percent of the respondents are from SadakathullahAppa College and 34.5 percent of the respondent St.Xavier'sCollege.So majority of the students belongs to St.Xavier's College.

3. Field of Study:Arts/Science

The level of Financial literacy can also vary based on the field of study taken that's either Arts or Science.

Table 3 : Field of Study

Sl. No.	Factor	Frequency	Percent
1	Arts	50	45.5
2	Science	60	54.5
	Total	110	100.0

Source: Primary Data.

The table 3 reveals that 45.5 percent of the respondents have chosen Arts as their field of studies and 54.5 percent of the respondent have chosen Science as their field of studies. So the majority of the respondents belongs to Science field of study with 54.5 percent.

4 Capability of Managing their own Finance:

Each and every respondents have their own spending habit as well as saving attitude. The Financial Literacy level of each and every respondent are been analysed on the basis of their age group that is 17years,18 – 20 years and 21- 25 years. According to the age group Capability of managing own finance keeps changing.

Table 4
Capability of Managing their own Finance

Sl.No.	Factor	Age Group			Total
		17 years	18-20 years	21-25 years	
1	Able to Manage own Finance	30 (71.4)	23 (71.9)	31 (86)	84 (76.4)
2	Not able to Manage own Finance	12 (28.6)	9 (28.1)	5 (14)	26 (23.6)
	Total	42 (100)	32 (100)	36 (100)	110 (100)

Source: Primary Data

The table 4 states that the respondent who were able to manage their own finance are 71.4 percent of the respondent belongs to the age of 17 years, 71.9 percent belongs to the age group of 18 – 20 years and 86 percent of the respondent belongs to the age group of 21 – 25 years. But the respondents who were not able to manage their own finance are 28.6 percent belongs to the age of group of 12 years, 28.1 percent of them are of age 18 – 20 years, 14 percent of them are of age 21 -25 years. Hence the majority of the respondent who were able to manage their own finance belongs to age of 21-25 years with 86 percent.

5.Opinion about how personal financial literacy can help students:

The table explains how the respondent has expressed their views regarding the personal financial literacy and how is it useful to their daily life as well as in future.

Table5:Opinion about how personal financial literacy can help Students

Sl. No.	Factor	Frequency	Percent
1	We can be avoided being victimized by financial crime.	30	27.3
2	To Learn the right method to invest for our future needs and buy the right kind.	16	14.5
3	To lead a financially secure life through forming healthy spending habits.	16	14.5
4	Do all of the Above.	48	43.6
	Total	110	100

Source: Primary Data

The table 5 reveals that 14.5 percent of the respondent have given their opinion as to lead a financially secured life through forming healthy spending habits and to Learn the right

method to invest for our future needs and buy the right kind. 27.3 percent of the respondent have given opinion that they can be avoided being victimized by financial crime. 43.6 percent of them agreed to possess all the above factors. Hence the majority of the respondent who has given their opinion is favoring all the above factors with 43.6 percent.

6H02 : Chi-Square Test:

Practicing of Managing Personal Finance.

Table 6 : Practicing of managing Personal Finance

Sl.No.	Factor	Age Group			Total	χ^2
		17 years	18-20 years	21-25 years		
1	I regularly set aside money each month as savings for future needs.	2.52	3.16	3.28	2.95	35.237
2	I compare prices when shopping for major expenses.	2.81	3.05	3.47	2.97	18.095
3	I use a spending plan or Budget.	2.27	2.82	2.99	2.53	20.010
4	I Always keep track of my expenditure and income.	2.74	3.09	3.45	2.93	20.010
5	Maintain adequate financial records.	2.06	2.60	3.01	2.39	19.568
6	Planning and implementing a regular Investment program.	2.25	2.46	2.76	2.34	8.088
7	Plan to spend less than the income.	2.16	2.21	3.26	2.43	30.590

Source: Primary Data . *Significant at the 5% Level.

The table 6 draws an inference that among all the factors ‘I always keep track of my expenditure and income ‘ and ‘I regularly set aside money each month as savings for future needs ‘is been practiced **always** by the respondent of age group **21-25 years** as it has the highest mean value of 3.45 and 3.28 , ‘I use a spending plan or Budget’ and ‘I compare prices when shopping for major expenses’ is been practiced by the respondent **sometimes** as it has a mean value of 2.99 (age group of **21-25 years**) and 2.81 (**17 years**), ‘ Planning and implementing a regular Investment program’ is done by the respondent **occasionally** with mean value of 2.76 belongs to age group of **21-25 years**, ‘ Plan to spend less than the income’ factor is been followed **rarely** as it has a mean value of 2.16 of the age group **17 years**, ‘Maintain adequate financial records’ is **never** been practiced by the respondents as it has mean value of 2.06 and belongs to the age group **17 years**.

Hence the majority of the respondents who have the practice of managing personal finance is Always with age group of 21-25 years and with mean value of 3.45 and have always agreed in practicing the factor 'I regularly set aside money each month as savings for future needs'

*Chi-Square Tests: Association between Age and Education

Null Hypothesis (H02):

H0	2	There is an association between Age group and practicing of managing personal finance.
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Analysis: Based on the Chi-Square test, the 'P' value is greater than 0.05 at 5% level of significance. Hence it is found that the Null Hypothesis is been rejected or the alternative Hypothesis is accepted for all the satisfaction level.

Discussion: So it is understood that there is an association between age group and practice of managing personal finance.

7. Awareness in various Investment Scheme

Table 7 : Awareness in various Investment Scheme

Sl. No.	Factor	Weighted Garrett Score	Weighted average Garrett Score	Rank
1	Bank Fixed Deposit	7188	65.34545	I
2	Real Estate	7040	64.00000	III
3	Post Office Saving Schemes	7075	64.31818	II
4	Insurance and Pension Plan(NPS)	5485	49.86364	IV
5	National Savings Certificates	4585	41.68182	V
6	Debentures and Bonds	4320	39.27273	VI
7	Gold and Silver	4176	37.96364	VII
8	Public Provident Fund	4131	37.55455	VIII

Source: Primary Data

The table 7 garret ranking technique reveals that I rank is secured for 'Bank fixed deposit', II rank is secured for Post office and saving schemes, III rank for real estate, IV the rank is secured for Insurance and Pension Plan, V rank is secured for National Savings Certificate, VI rank for Debentures and Bonds, VII rank is secured for Gold and Silver, VIII rank Public Provident Fund.

8.H02: ONE WAY ANOVA:

Assessing Investment knowledge with features of various investments:

Table 8 :Frequency of knowing

SL. No	Factors	Field of study		Total	F-Statistics
		Arts	Science		
1	Rate of Interests offered on fixed deposits by various banks are same	2.18	1.98	2.07	1.717
2	Rate of Interest offered on Fixed deposits is calculated under compound interest method	2.20	2.08	2.14	0.498
3	National Saving Certificate is a long term risk free investment	2.40	2.27	2.33	0.641
4	No Minimum and Maximum limit of investment made in PPF per year.	1.84	1.70	1.76	1.220
5	Employee provident fund is applicable to salaried employees only	2.44	2.13	2.27	3.036
6	The Return that the owner of a share receives is known as earnings per share	2.20	1.85	2.01	3.772
7	POMIS Investment is not guaranteed by the Indian Government.	1.48	1.42	1.45	0.302
8	Life insurance policy is transferrable in nature.	1.36	1.73	1.56	5.455

Source: Primary Data .***Significant at the 5% level**

The table 8 reveals that most of the respondents of Arts group have marked as true for all the above features of the various Investment than compared to the Science students.

The above analysis has been further tested with One Way Analysis of Variance in order to know the difference among the major field of study Arts and Science Students and their Investment knowledge.

ONE-WAY ANOVA***Analysis:**

The F-statistics results of above table 8 reveals that the null hypothesis is accepted as the 'p' value is higher than 0.05 levels for all the factors and the Null hypothesis is rejected for factors such as "Rate of Interest offered on Fixed deposits is calculated under compound interest method" and "Investment in POMIS is not guaranteed by the Government of India as the 'p' value is lesser than the 0.05 level".

***Discussion:**

1. There is no significant difference between the major field of studies with regard to all factors. 2. There is significant difference for factors "Rate of Interest offered on Fixed deposits calculated in compound interest method" and "POMIS Investment is not guaranteed

by the Indian Government ".Hence there is significant difference between the major field of studies and various Investment Schemes and the Major Field of Studies of Arts and Science.

9.Save money for future from the Salary .

Table 9 :Save money for future from the Salary .

Sl. No.	Factor	Frequency	Percent
1	Strongly Agree	32	29.1
2	Agree	50	45.5
3	Neither agree Nor disagree	24	21.8
4	Disagree	4	3.6
5	Strongly Disagree	0	0
	Total	110	100.0

Source: Primary Data

The Table 9 shows that the majority of the respondent have agreed to save from their salary for their future with 45.5 percent.29.1 percent of the respondent have strongly agreed to save for their future.21.8 percent of the respondents have neither agreed nor disagreed. 3.6 percent of them have disagreed to do saving from their salary. Non of them have strongly disagreed to save for their future.Hence the majority of the respondent have agreed to save money for their future from salary with highest percent of 45.5.

Findings

- Major segments of the respondents in this study is female.
- Most of the respondents belongs to St.Xavier's College.
- The respondents belongs to Science field of study with 54.5 percent.
- The Respondent who were able to manage their own finance belongs to age of 21-25 years with 86 percent.
- The majority of the respondent has given their opinion about how personal financial literacy can helpin favoring all the factors given with 43.6 percent.
- Majority of the respondents with age group of 21-25 years have the practice of managing personal finance .They use to regularly set aside money each month as savings for future needs.
- Among various investment Schemes the respondent have more awareness in 'Bank Fixed Deposit'.
- The respondents of Arts group have marked correctly as true for all the above features of the various Investment than compared to the Science students.

- The majority of the respondent have agreed to save money for their future from salary.

Suggestion:

- Various measures should be taken to train both arts and science students at college by means of conducting financial awareness programs like seminars, lectures on money management and prepare Budget for spending.
- All Financial Institutions like Postal Services / Banks must hold and awareness programs for college students .
- All Financial Organizations like Postal services/Banks should conduct awareness programs at schools, colleges and various institutions even in rural areas to improve the financial knowledge to handle personal finance among every youth.
- All students should be encouraged to improve their savings habit

Conclusion and Discussion:

Financial Literacy plays an important role for the students to plan their savings ,to teach them how to spend their pocket-money and train them to save their money in proper investment scheme for their future studies etc.As the Financial markets have been increased very widely and complex each and every students should be given proper financial knowledge to choose the right financial products.Financial education will improve the skill and knowledge and safeguard from harmful practices.The result of this study shows that majority of the students of age group of 17years were able to manage their finance.Most of the students of age group of 21-25 years has the habit of saving for their future.Among various Investment Schemes students has more awareness about “Bank Fixed Deposit”.Arts group students have more awareness in all Investment schemes than compared to Science students.Finally,Majority of the students have agreed to save money for their future.Students at college level should take proper financial decisions which will be an important influence on their personal finance after their college which will be an ultimate affect on their academic performance.

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